
SOCIO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF USERS OF CREDIT ON CASSAVA BASED PRODUCTION SYSTEMS IN DELTA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This paper assessed the socio-economic analysis of micro-credit on cassava-based production systems in Delta State. This was done with a view to providing relevant information for policy formulation and development. A stratified sampling procedure was employed in selecting respondents from 13 Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Delta State from which primary data were collected using structured questionnaires. The tools used for the analysis were descriptive and quantitative. The study showed women were more involved in credit use. There was also an ageing population in the production of cassava. It also showed that majority of farmers who were involved in credit use could read and write and so were able to fill the forms for loan requests. This paper concludes by calling for the support of both public and private bodies for the development of credit use in cassava farming.

KEYWORDS: Socio-economic, micro-credit, cassava, local farmers, employment, incomes, Delta State

INTRODUCTION

Cassava provides good quality carbohydrate, which may be substituted for maize or barley and its ration are especially suitable for swine dairy and poultry production (Oshin, 2003). The ability of the cassava crop include to substitute for feed grain imports, to supply calories to the poorest sector of the society, to increase incomes for resource poor small-scale farmers with marginal land resources and to provide employment in processing activities, convert the cassava crop into the efficient agricultural policy instrument and a vehicle for poverty alleviation. The rationale for the choice of cassava crop rests on the premise that cassava production remains the mainstay of the traditional economy for which adequate capital is required.

There is an increasing need to develop the use of credit in cassava production. The present unfavourable economic reality has informed Government to accord a high priority to the development of small and medium scale agricultural enterprises. Micro credit that is focused on the achievement of equitable and sustainable gain has been agreed to be the key element for the 21st century's economic and social development (Rahman, 1999). It is for this reason that many bilateral and multilateral development agencies incorporate micro-credit into their development projects. Despite these efforts, agricultural production is yet to match the needs of either the growing population or the expanding agro-based industrial sector. Though capital is just one many factors that influence agricultural performance, the apparent complete irresponsiveness of production to the enormous efforts of the Federal Government in the area of credit infusion underlines the need for new approaches for addressing the problem of adequate capital in the sector.

This paper attempts to make some suggestions that would lead to the rapid development of the industry which can be answered through constant research. It has been reported that very few empirical studies have been carried out in this regard (Schreiner and Nagaragen, 1997).

The objective of this paper is to identify the socio-economic characteristics of users of credit on cassava production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study covered users of credit in cassava production in 13 LGAs of Delta State. All three Senatorial districts were chosen to give state wide coverage. Five LGAs were each randomly selected from Delta North (Aniocha North and South, Ukuani, Ndokwa West and Ika South East) and Delta Central (Ethiope East and West, Isoko North and South and Ughelli South). Three LGAs were selected from Delta South-Warri North and South and Warri South-West. A total of 164 copies

of questionnaires were returned out of 260 administered. 96 of them were users of credit. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and tables. In terms of coverage the study area represents about 50% of the state.

Primary and secondary data were used to generate information for this study. The Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) and Ministry of Commerce and Industry provided a comprehensive list of users of micro credit. The primary data were obtained through the use of structured interviews scheduled for non-literate ones. In the collection of primary data, well-structured and pre-tested questionnaires were administered through personal interviews by the researcher and twelve trained ADP enumerators. The characteristics of the farmers include gender, age, household size, marital status, educational level, farming experience and farm size.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cassava based farmers were those that used micro credit to finance their activities. The characteristics of those respondents were found to have effect on micro credit use. These characteristics are discussed below.

GENDER

Of the 96 users of credit, 68 (70.8%) were females as against 28 (29.1%) males. There seems, therefore, to be female dominance in credit use for cassava production as presented in Table 1. This suggests that women are observed to be more involved in credit use for cassava production. This result agrees with findings of Shreiner and Nagarajan (1997) in their study of credit worthiness of borrowers where females were found to be likely-to borrow than males.

The gender distributions of respondents deviate from the norm since men are supposed to participate more in agriculture and then credit. The higher proportion of females in cassava farming in Delta state may be due to the fact that processing of cassava is more generally seen as jobs associated with the women folk. Apart from that, most members of the cooperatives and thrift societies were observed to be women, which may have put them at an advantage in assessing credit. The role of women in agriculture and credit is becoming more prominent as revealed by the findings of this study. Women have become more interested in productive agriculture as against what was obtained in the past where women were associated only with the processing and marketing of agricultural produce.

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY GENDER

USERS	NUMBER	%
FEMALE	68	70.8
MALE	28	29.2
TOTAL	96	100.0

Source: Field Survey.

AGE:

The ages of the farmers ranged from 25 years to 70 with a mean of 46 years. Very few (6) of the farmers were below age 30 years.

This is an indication that generally, young people are not heavily involved in cassava production. This could be due to the fact that the age bracket of 30 and below are mainly expected to still be in school. Majority of the respondents (35% to 37%) were in the age bracket of 41-50 years. Twenty five (25%) were between 51 and 60 years and 9 (9.4%) were above 60 years of age.

The age structure presented in Table 2 indicates an aged population of cassava-based farmers in Delta state. This result agrees with the findings of Erhabor *et al*, (2004) in which cassava farmers were described as ageing.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY AGE.

AGE	FREQUENCY	%
>30	6	6.3
31-40	21	21.9
41-50	35	36.5
51-60	25	26.0
61	9	9.4
TOTAL	96	100.0

MARITAL STATUS

As presented in Table 3, 14 (14.5%) among the respondents were single, 69 (71.9%) married while others were widowed. The higher percentage of married couples has implication for agricultural development. This may indicate more labour hands for farming activities.

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY MARITAL STATUS

MARITAL STATUS	FREQUENCY	%
SINGLE	14	14.5
MARRIED	69	71.9
WIDOWED	11	11.5
OTHERS	2	2.1
TOTAL	96	100.0

FARMING EXPERIENCE

The farming experience of respondents is presented in Table 4. The highest number of respondents, 28 (29.2%) of them, had farming experience of between 11 and 14 years. Twenty-three (24%) respondents had between 15 and 19 years of experience. Their years of experience could have informed them of the need of capital formation through micro-credit.

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY FARMING EXPERIENCE

FARMING EXPERIENCE	FREQUENCY	%
>5	10	10.4
6-10	26	27.1
11-14	28	29.1
15-19	23	24.0
<20	9	9.4
TOTAL	96	100.0

EDUCATION

The level of education may indicate productivity potential both on and off farm. The more educated a farmer is, the more likely he is to work off the farm. Many studies contend that farmer education influence farm productivity by affecting a farmer’s input and output decision.

In Delta state, only 7(7.3%) of the respondents had no formal education. Twenty-seven (28.1%) had incomplete primary school while only 10(10.4%) completed primary school. 45(46.9%) had secondary to Tertiary education.

The results showed that most respondents could read and write and so could fill the basic forms to request for loan from credit sources. More educated farmers tend to know better about the sources of credit available and the procedures involved in each of them. They are also more likely to manage their resources.

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY EDUCATION.

LEVEL	FREQUENCY	%
NO, FORMAL SCHOOL	7	7.3
INCOMPLETE PRY. SCHOOL	7	7.3
INCOMPLETE SEC. SCHOOL	27	28.1
COMPLETE PRY. SCHOOL	10	10.4
COMPLETE SEC. SCHOOL	23	24.0
OND/NCE	15	15.6
B.SC/BA/HND	6	6.3
POST GRADUATE	1	1.0
TOTAL	96	100.0
MEAN	10.72	

HOUSEHOLD SIZE

The result of the study showed that the household sizes were fairly large in Delta state with a mean of seven persons per household as presented in Table 6. Large households tend to have high financial needs which may have prompted them to increase production by way of credit.

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY HOUSEHOLD SIZE

SIZE (PERSONS)	FREQUENCY	%
1-4	28	29.3
5-9	59	60.5
10-14	7	7.3
>15	2	2.2
TOTAL	96	100.0

FARM SIZE

The farm size reported by cassava farmers in Delta state ranged from one hectare to about 5 hectares with a mean of 2.6 hectares. Thirty five (36.5%) had farm sizes of between 1-1.99 hectares while twenty nine (30.2%) cultivated between 2-2.99 hectares. The results as presented in Table 7 show that majority of the farmers were operating on small-scale levels. This could be land acquisition problems which discriminate against land holdings by individuals (especially women) and partly due to insufficient credit. There is now considerable consensus that lending to the poor can succeed provided it is accompanied by other services, especially training, information, and access to land. In some of the lowest income countries, lack of access to land is the most critical single cause of rural poverty, which dominates the poverty situation in these countries. Yet, few countries have substantial land reform programmes.

TABLE 7: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY FARM SIZE.

FARM SIZE	FREQUENCY	%
0.1-1 ha	-----	-----
1-1.99	35	36.5
2-2.99	29	30.2
3-3.99	12	12.5
4-4.99	13	13.5
>5	7	7.3
TOTAL	96	100.0
MEAN	2.6	

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper has shown that women are more involved in credit use in the case of cassava production. It also showed an aged population that is able to read and write.

Majority of the farmers were operating on small-scale levels which could be due to land acquisition patterns that discriminate against large holdings by individuals.

The development of the credit sector on cassava farming needs the support of everybody. This includes the efforts of the government, banks, private individuals, cooperative societies, and non-governmental organizations. For example, access to credit needs to be supplemented with access to land and appropriate technology. This view is precipitated on the fact that Nigeria holds an important position in the economic and political spheres on the African Continent.

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